

A Collaborative Auto- Ethnographical Study on the Emerging Phenomena of the 21st Century Practice- Teaching Journey

Louie P. Gula¹, Jayrome L. Nuñez²

¹Saint Joseph College, Southern Leyte, Philippines.

²Baliuag University, Bulacan, Philippines.

Abstract – This research study aims to highlight the personal experiences encountered by the participants, compare the differences between both narrations, and lastly identify common phenomena. This study utilized the auto-ethnographical research study. Ellis and Bochner (2000) describe autoethnography as “an autobiographical form of writing that exhibits several levels of awareness, linking the personal to the cultural”. Autoethnography may include a wide variety of topics, from personal research experiences to parallel explorations of the researcher’s and participants’ experiences, as well as the researcher’s experience while undertaking a particular piece of research (Ellis & Bochner, 2000; Maso, 2001). It appears that practice teaching enables interns to experience the actual classroom teaching and school paperwork preparation. Aside from the technical aspects of the internship process, it prepares the student-teachers as well in the different course of school activities that will immerse them in the process of management. Generally, the personal experiences of the different interns vary from the school environment, protocols, and learning resources of the school assigned. The different practice- teaching experiences narrated by the interns that will have a common phenomenon will be a strong determinant of a certain situation.

Keywords: Autoethnography, Personal Experiences, Practice- teaching, Teaching internship, Collaboration, Practice- Teachers.

1.INTRODUCTION

This auto- ethnographical study is about having a whole memory of achieving and fulfilling the feeling of becoming a teacher. It allows us to express our feelings and thoughts toward our students, our teachers, and the school staff. It also helped us express our impressions and thoughts by portraying the things that happened during our internship and the series of school activities with our teachers, to the school staff. It also helped us express our impressions and thoughts by portraying the things that happened during our internship and the series of school activities in which we were involved. Those things helped us and shaped our skills and capabilities which were a great foundation for our journey in the field of teaching. Teaching involves emotional tendencies that require emotional labor, which is defined as the manifestation of emotions during interpersonal interactions. Emotional labor is at the core of the desire to teach. Emotional practices are linked to professional happiness and health, as well as the burnout that many teachers face, which may lead to their leaving the field (Zembylas, 2005).

This study describes our strengths and weaknesses as practice teachers which shows our stability in facing struggles that entirely molded us to become better and more productive individuals. It also highlights different kinds of emotions we experienced like frustrations, doubt, happiness, and most of all uncertainties. Despite those mixed emotions that surrounded us, we were able to conquer and remember our aims of reaching our ambitions of becoming a teacher someday.

Moreover, it also shows how we interacted and got along with the school staff and teachers that we considered as one of the instruments that molded our abilities into becoming effective teachers. Teaching practice is about more than simply knowing what to teach and how to teach; it's also about growing as a teacher. Interpersonal, pedagogical, intercultural, and psychological abilities are among the skills required of a trainee teacher (Owuama, 2017).

In general, this study serves as an overview of the progress of our work and performance. Not only as a future educator but also as an individual it aims to describe how we handled the things as students, as a teacher, and as a person. Our whole interaction with the school staff and with our cooperating teachers. All the experiences highlighted in this study are pieces of evidence of the knowledge gained and competencies acquired throughout the years of training and professional growth.

Research Questions:

1. What are the common misconceptions about teaching internships?
2. What are the differences between having an internship in a public school from a private school?
3. What are the challenges faced by the practice teachers during the internship?
4. How do practice teachers develop skills during internships?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Teaching Practice (TP) is a key course in which teacher education institutes send student-teachers to various schools to put what they've learned into practice under the observation of experienced instructors. "Teaching practice can be defined as the system by which teachers in training are subjected to a systematic exposure to the actual classroom situation," according to Davidson (2005). Similarly, Elmabruk (2020) defined teaching practice as "the opportunity given to trainee teachers to apply the knowledge and skills they acquired during their education."

However, looking at the vision and mission of several teacher preparation institutions around the world, it becomes clear that the main goal for those institutions is to prepare teachers to be able to teach using modern teaching methods and technology. This can only be accomplished by providing student teachers with sufficient theoretical information besides classroom experience (Owuama, 2017). As a result, TP is regarded as a cornerstone in the teaching and learning program at Tripoli University's Faculty of Education, since student instructors must demonstrate their competencies and capabilities in implementing the information and ideas they have gained throughout their studies. In their last semester of college, student teachers commonly go for teaching practice, which lasts around six weeks and includes one week of observation and five weeks of actual teaching. They are given chances to do some micro-teaching in college with their classmates; each student must conduct at least two lessons in front of the course teacher; and they get constructive comments from classmates and the course instructor based on their performance in micro-teaching (Elmabruk, 2018).

Only those who pass the teaching techniques I and II courses are eligible for teaching practice in schools the next semester, therefore each student-teacher must give at least 8 to 10 sessions each week, each lasting 40 minutes, for a total of 50 minutes.

Each student teacher is supervised and assessed by two supervisors: an Academic Supervisor (AS) from the department that the student-teacher belongs to, and an Education Supervisor (ES) from the Education and Psychology Department. The final assessment mark by the AS is given out of 50, to which the ES adds 40 marks, and the TP school headmaster adds another 10 marks, for a total of 100 percent (Elmabruk, 2018).

Although most student teachers see teaching practice as an exciting event in their life and look forward to stepping in front of a class of students and putting what they have learned over their

lengthy academic careers into practice, it is not without its difficulties and obstacles. As a result, numerous academics from many settings have examined in depth the obstacles that student-teachers face throughout their teaching practice. Sarçobana (2010), for example, cited various problems that student teachers encounter in their TP, including putting theories into practice, selecting an effective teaching approach, and determining whether learning goals were accomplished or not. Among the problems were a lack of facilities and extra resources in schools, as well as misunderstandings on the side of the school administration. Aside from that, dealing with a large class, having a bad lesson plan, and creating differentiated assignments were also prevalent (Ball et al., 2008; Scott, 2015). Al-(2016) Momani's research at KSA looked at teaching practice problems at the Faculty of Education from the viewpoints of supervisors and pre-service teachers. Fear of teaching, communication skills, and putting ideas into practice were all identified as typical problems. Furthermore, student instructors had difficulty organizing their class time, according to Nasir and Zafar (2018).

That example, allocating sufficient time for each task without spending excessive time reviewing students' assignments, providing directions, and collecting attendance. They also said that some student teachers continued to act as if they were university students, preferring to be considered as directors by the school administration, maybe because they were unaware of the terms and circumstances of discipline and the school code of conduct. They did remark, however, that 75% of the participants were interested in teaching and had attempted a variety of teaching approaches other than those used in schools. They also saw the student instructors' eagerness to interact with their supervisors to get timely feedback. Interestingly, some student teachers attempted to establish a positive relationship with their students without maintaining sufficient distance between them and the students, and as a result, they did not receive

sufficient respect from students, who saw them as university students rather than teachers (Owuama, 2017).

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This study utilized the auto-ethnographical research study. Ellis and Bochner (2000) describe autoethnography as "an autobiographical form of writing that exhibits several levels of awareness, linking the personal to the cultural". There are several definitions of the phrase, which vary depending on the researcher's own experience and the topic under inquiry (Foster et al., 2006). Autoethnography may include a wide variety of topics, from personal research experiences to parallel explorations of the researcher's and participants' experiences, as well as the researcher's experience while undertaking a particular piece of research (Ellis & Bochner, 2000; Maso, 2001).

According to McIlveen (2008), the key aspect of autoethnography is that it "...involves the scientist or practitioner undertaking narrative analysis relative to oneself or herself as closely tied to a specific event". As a result, it's not only about writing about oneself; it's also about being critical of one's own experiences in the formation of the research project or one's interaction with the issue under investigation. (1) The function of the autoethnography in the narrative: is the autoethnography an insider or an outsider of the phenomena being described? (2) The role of autoethnography in the narrative: is the autoethnography an insider or an outsider of the phenomenon being described? (2) Whose voice is being heard: the persons who are being investigated or the researcher? (3) Cultural displacement: persons who have been moved from their native habitat owing to political or societal difficulties express certain facts. Although autoethnography may be addressed in a variety of ways, I'd prefer to stick with Ellis' (2007) definition: 'Doing autoethnography includes a back-and-forth movement between experiencing and probing a

vulnerable self and observing and exposing the larger context of that experience.

The information gathered via this sort of reflection on our own lives and experiences might be expressed as a poem, a narrative, or a tale (Nekvapil, 2003). As a result, autoethnography's rhetorical style varies, from formal literary pieces to more casual reports or anecdotes. Some writers believe that researchers must convey stories (Wolcott, 1994). Others believe autoethnography should be able to captivate the minds and emotions of readers (Ellis, 2000). There seem to be no formal guidelines for creating an autoethnographic narrative since what matters is the meaning, not the construction of a highly scholarly book.

Anderson (2006) distinguishes between analytic and evocative autoethnography to attract researchers' attention to the differences in the practice of what is referred to as "evocative or emotive autoethnography." He advocated a more analytical kind of autoethnography...in which the researcher is (1) a full part of the study group or setting, (2) visible as such in published materials, and (3) devoted to the development of theoretical understandings of larger social phenomena.

As a result, analytic autoethnography focuses on objective writing and analysis of a certain group, while evocative autoethnography focuses on researchers' introspection on a specific issue for readers to connect with the researchers' thoughts and experiences. In a different vein, Foley (2002) argues for more reflective epistemological and narrative approaches, believing that these will help to create auto ethnographies a more engaging and common genre, bridging the gap between scholars and ordinary people. "On the whole, autoethnography don't want you to sit back as spectators; they want readers to feel and care and want," said Bochner and Ellis (1996). Because the link, offers readers their own experiences, evocative or emotive autoethnography seems to be gaining popularity among academics. However, in addition

to its benefits as a research technique, it has drawbacks and critiques that must be addressed.

4.SAMPLING AND PARTICIPANT

The participants of this study come from different school environments with different setups and settings. Both are currently pursuing their doctoral studies in prestigious universities.

Louie P. Gula is a teacher-researcher in the Junior High School Department at Saint Joseph College, Maasin City Southern Leyte. He earned his Master of Education major in Physical Education minor in English at the Visayas State University. He is currently enrolled in a Doctor of Education program majoring in Educational Management at Philippine Christian University, an autonomous university as per CHED CMO 7, series of 2021.

Jayrome Nuñez graduated with his bachelor's degree back in 2010. He is currently a lecturer in a technical and higher institution in Saudi Arabia. He earned his master's degree in Educational Management from Araullo University. Currently pursuing his Ed.D. in Educational Management at Baliuag University, an autonomous university as per CHED CMO 7, series of 2021.

4.1 Data Collection

This study utilized the descriptive/self-affirmative type of research which is in the form of a collaborative-autoethnography method. In this study, we narrate our personal experiences with an analysis of the phenomenon. Collaboration invites many voices and viewpoints into the study, and it expands the source of data and information from a single researcher to several researchers, resulting in a deeper knowledge and learning of oneself and others (Chang et al.,2013)

5.RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 The Public-School Environment

Louie P. Gula as practice teacher from a public secondary high school

5.2 The School Building

This public secondary high school is one of the schools located in Hindang, Leyte. It can be seen along the highway on the right side going to Baybay City. It is composed of 46 personnel, including 45 teachers and 1 non-teaching staff. It has grade levels from grade 7 up to grade 12 and this includes senior high school. There are 6 sections in grade 7, 3 sections from grade 8 to grade 10, 4 sections in grade 11, and 5 sections in grade 12. Grade 7 offers a special program in the arts with 4 offered sections, visual arts, dance, music, and theater. There are also 2 academic tracks for the senior high school department offering ABM and TVL. A total of 24 classrooms are found inside the campus.

Upon entering the campus, some quotations were found outside the school wall with paintings on it like "God always forgives, man sometimes forgives but Mother Earth never forgives". These are not just mere quotations, but they will help you reflect and learn from them. These quotations prove that students will not just simply walk but with lived-up lessons in life. Moreover, the school has a green-painted gate and a guardhouse which serves as the monitoring site for all the school staff and students. The office of the school admin where the principal stays is also the room where the staff log in and out and record their time of arrival and departure in and out of the school campus.

Aside from that, classrooms have desired ventilation which makes them conducive to learning. Some of the classrooms look perfectly fine. The school has 6 comfort rooms, which are available to be used. Some students stay on the bench during their free time and most of them stay in the gym to play basketball and volleyball. During recess, there are also 2 canteens inside the school where some of the students hang out.

Two-Storey buildings are built for the senior high school and a newly built building for the TVL-SMAW. It has a stage with a painting on it facing the half-roofed gym enough for the events to be carried out.

5.3 Laboratory Buildings

Moreover, it has a 2-computer laboratory which has a complete set of computers that are used for students' practical exams, classes, research, and assignments. The 2-computer laboratory shares a 1-WIFI for internet connection which is readily available. These effective tools strengthen the academic foundation of students in terms of research papers and other works. It has also a room for the science laboratory accommodated with newly-delivered apparatuses for experiments and science activities.

5.4 School Library

The school has a library which is one of the sources of information, which covers only minimal references for research due to the lack of books but still it offers accessible materials readily available for the students to use. The library is also used as our office for doing schoolwork, lesson plans, and instructional materials. The library is well-decorated and ventilated, convenient for the students for studying. It has a wide area enough to accommodate several students. It is also used as an office for school paper journalism.

5.5 School Clinic

The school has a clinic in case of some accidents or emergency cases. It offers medicines and a first aid kit that could be used in times of accidents.

Furthermore, the school has different corresponding departments in each field, such as the Math department, Science department, Filipino department, MAPEH department, and ICT department. This designates the different assigned tasks in every activity held in school. In addition, the staff and teachers actively participate in all school activities and do their corresponding responsibilities.

Generally, the school has a pleasing physical environment that is eco-friendly and conducive to learning. An important factor of the productiveness of both teachers and students adds to meaningful learning and experiences. The students' performance proves the quality of education that the high school provides to the students which

makes the school popular and most enrolled by the Hindanganons and also students coming from Inopacan.

5.6 Teacher's Contemplation of the School Environment

Being assigned to this secondary high school was an uncertain feeling since it's not my alma mater considering the agreement that we will be assigned to the high school we graduated from. Most especially the distance between the school which is in Hindang from my hometown in Matalom, which is quite far. But due to the protocol being released and implemented by the Visayas State University, College of Education, and Department of Teacher Education management we had to abide by the rules.

From the very first time that I entered the campus, I was amazed and excited because of the school grounds, the infrastructure, and the number of students as well. Nothing to be worried about in the area assigned but to expect great things from this school. And I'm still thankful for being assigned to this prestigious high school in Hindang.

During our deployment, my co-student teachers and I were warmly welcomed by the faculty and staff. Before we were assigned to the different classrooms for observations, we were oriented by the MAPEH department about the school's policies and agreements. It was an exhilarating feeling to be greeted by the students but it was awkward at first as those were the first experiences we had been greeted with like an actual teacher. After the orientation, we were turned over to the assigned coordinator for the designation of classes. The school has a special program in the arts in which there are 3 of us assigned 3 programs, music, dance, and theater. Afterward, we were oriented on our assigned cooperating teachers for the schedule of classes.

I was assigned to the Special Program in the Arts dance classroom; it was a well-ventilated and well-lit room. I noticed that the school facilities were

organized and well-equipped for students' learning. The school library and computer laboratory gave students easy access to research and school projects needed for the lessons. It has also a mini-clinic offering several medicines that could help the students in case of emergency.

To wrap it up, the school facilities are very important and useful for the learnings of the students that should be gained necessary for their future studies. These things are steppingstones for the students to gain confidence and surpass the ignorance of technologies and innovation and be equipped for the future.

5.7 Lesson Planning

Lesson Planning is one of the most essential work plans by the teachers where it serves as a framework or blueprint for the lesson to be delivered. It is one of the tools used by teachers to have the desired protocol and proper management inside the classroom to conduct an organized flow of discussions. Creating a daily lesson plan is a frustrating and difficult job due to the merged ideas of the lessons to be delivered. It is necessary to give one's full attention and concentration to make the discussions effectively delivered in the teaching-learning process. It requires effort and time to plan a daily lesson plan as well as learning activities. It is the best way of making the class discussion well-prepared and successful planning that can overall supply students' needs like knowledge, skills, and most especially values. As a practice teacher, it's my responsibility to always make a lesson plan before delivering a lesson to my students. Before my job as a practice teacher, I exerted most of my ideas and effort in making my lesson plan and class discussion worthwhile.

After every correction to my lesson plan, I'll rephrase it and change the suggested ideas by my cooperating teacher. I used 4A's lesson plan since it is the format that the school is following. The 4A lesson plan still has five parts: the objective, subject matter, procedure, evaluation, and assignment.

The first part of my lesson plan is the objective which shows the expected learning outcomes that the students should acquire at the end of the course study. These are the goals to be achieved by the students in connection with the lesson of the day. The second part is the subject matter which includes the topic of content, references, and materials that will be used in the delivery of the lesson. Next, is the procedure part which comprises of 4A's, the Activity, Analysis, Abstraction, and Application. The activities must correlate to the expected learning outcomes of the lesson wherein the participation and exploration occur. In the analysis part, the data and information from the activity conducted by the students are being processed and examined systemically. However, in abstraction, the concept or generalization of the topic must be interpreted by students. It could be in the form of questions. In application, the lesson learned must be applied in practical or real-life situations. The fourth part of the lesson is the evaluation where students are being assessed whether they understand and learned from the discussion. And the last one is the assignment, whether you are going to give an assignment as practice or research for future use.

In general, lesson planning molds me to become an efficient and effective teacher and as such. Having a lesson plan enhanced my capabilities in converting learnings into skills and transforming strategies into effective deliberation. I also improved my confidence in facing my students and teachers. Even though I still lack the enhancement of my communication skills, I was still able to face my audiences with maximum confidence and positivity. With the overflowing comments and suggestions of my cooperating teachers, I was greatly thankful for surpassing the challenges and problems crossed. Making a lesson plan is tiring and disturbing but despite its nature, I'm still grateful for it helped me in planning and drawing actual scenarios that might happen inside the classroom.

5.8 Teacher's Contemplation on Lesson Preparation

When I entered and took my steps on the school ground of my cooperating school there, I decided that it will and will be my fate. I knew from the start that teaching is not as easy as slicing cake and pouring juice, it is beyond baking cake starting from the separation of its recipe which is the beginning of my very journey that day. I know that I no longer have the time to watch movies and play digital games because maybe most of my time would be diverted to practicing as an effective teacher.

One of the tools in having an efficient and effective discussion is by making a daily lesson plan, that will serve as a weapon in making class discussion ideal and realistic. It helps attain the desired flow of discussion which will make teaching effective and successful. Planning a lesson is not easy due to the accuracy and assurance that every part of the lesson was constructed and planned well to have a desirable outcome. Most of the time, I had some doubts and confusion in making my lessons but thanks to my cooperating teachers for the smart comments and suggestions on what to do on my lesson plan. I was thankful also to them because they never turned their back on me whenever I needed help. They gave me various advice on how to enhance and improve my skills in lesson plan writing. They also challenged me to do better every time and to monitor progress on my work. My lesson planning experience was indeed a memorable and informative one. I was so grateful also to my cooperating teachers because they portrayed friendliness and openness. They are so approachable that anytime I could talk to them regarding my lessons.

In general, in making a lesson plan I realized that it needs dedication and determination in creating it. It is very important to know what the things are you like to happen in your lesson and what are the things you expect from them. I should never be discouraged when mistakes cross my work, aside from those mistakes it is important to learn from them. I have to treat those things positively as a stepping stone and to make things better as I go along my journey of becoming an effective teacher

someday. Most especially, I must believe in myself that I can do things if I want to.

5.9 Teaching Assessment

The authority and power that comes from the teacher will not just simply mean teaching a person as an individual and as a learner, teaching requires great responsibilities that need special engagement. You have no special power to use to make your student learn but only your empty hands and bare minds to let your students understand the topic that you are discussing. There are much bigger challenges in teaching the students to make them more competitive and well-rounded individuals in the future.

Every day, the teacher checks and monitors the student's performance in the form of assignments, quizzes, exam papers, projects, skill notebooks, and daily attendance. I realized that becoming a teacher is not just teaching. I experienced stress and pressure day and night and always kept every record of my students updated. I also made sure that I kept every progress of their work so that I could identify the improvements in their output. All conducted exams and quizzes were recorded to monitor the student's performance and assess their level of understanding of a particular topic. Even though the day of teaching is very stressful and tiring I was still able to smile seeing the scores of my students improving and progressing. Somehow other students will not get a higher score and some are not listening to my discussion but still, overall, they got a passing score. After the evaluation, I reflected and reviewed my way of teaching. I also realized some of my mistakes and lapses carrying out the lesson to be improved next time. The low scores of my students somehow challenged me to improve myself and enabled me to think of varied strategies that can be used in my demonstration. I also took positively the challenges I will be able to recover from the negative comments.

Moreover, the learner's work will reflect the way how I taught my students whether I'm a failure or I improved something efficiently. I made sure to

guide and give them desirable feedback so that they will realize their improvements. It is difficult to assume that everybody in the class will get a higher score or even passing scores because of the differences between the students and the varied intelligence with different needs. I can you assure that they learned something from me due to their portrayed willingness and passion. They performed their responsibilities properly. They had also the eagerness and the interest to explore more and learn things.

Aside from that, I'm still happy and amazed that my students gave their positive and negative feedback on my teaching style and teaching strategies. I am glad about the positive comments and feedback from my students and I also made sure that they will learn from me and I will take their suggestions whole-heartedly. I am also glad about the negative comments because they will serve as a tool for my progress and so that I can locate my weaknesses and where to improve.

In general, I appreciated all the efforts and suggestions that the students and teachers gave us. I was happy for their welcoming and pleasing treatment as if we were one of the faculty and staff of the school. All of those things helped me and made me realize to embrace the profession of teaching.

5.10 Actual Lesson Delivery

My supervisor conducted the first observation. The moment when I first entered the room with my cooperating teacher and my supervisor, I felt numbing in my body and I could almost hear my heartbeat due to nervousness. I am thinking that this is it, no matter what happens I need to accept the things that will follow. It is very different when you are in front discussing the lesson normally without someone watching you from the special demonstration wherein people are observing your actions. It's like I'm going to burst any second. Nevertheless, it gave me an immediate impulse to act normally and speak straight. I have to prove to myself that I can do it even when pressures are

rising. I tried to deliver the lesson properly with ease and controlled the classroom like a professional one. I can see what is happening in my peripheral vision, where my supervisor wrote down the ratings and comments. I can also feel the aura of my cooperating teacher that reminds me of staying calm and going on no matter what while my performance was being rated. The rating that I will get will just automatically reflect how and what I did inside the classroom in the meantime.

I can feel that my cooperating teacher was wishing me luck while rating my performance. He tried also to calm me and advised me to relax and release all the anxiety. After the demonstration, my cooperating teacher and my supervisor commented on my performance and complimented me as well. I was so glad to hear those kinds of comments despite the feeling of uncertainty and doubt. But still, they said that I was able to recover from the corners of nervousness. Overall, they commented that I am ready for this kind of profession.

Some of the scores were just okay as it is, but the majority of the ratings were satisfying and encouraging. Though some parts of my demonstration needed improvements, overall, it was already above average. These evaluation forms served as a tool to determine my strengths and weaknesses in different areas of the teaching profession. Using these, I can locate the criterion that needs improvement and those that are already okay. It also helped me to be aware of the qualities that the teacher should have to be an efficient and effective one.

Through the evaluation forms, I was able to suffice and improved my daily teaching and demonstration. I also progressed my way of controlling the classroom and managing the students to listen to my discussion. I also boosted my self-confidence, and I was able to go out of the classroom with contentment. In a teaching-learning process, I learned from my students, and they also learned from me. I was able also to apply the

lessons in real-life scenarios in practical life. It helped me to discover new strategies and techniques to be used in teaching that made the flow of the lesson easy and meaningful. Without the rating scales and evaluation forms, I won't be able to determine my weaknesses and areas of my demonstration that needs attention. I could not also improve my teaching and my performance will not progress over time. These evaluation forms helped me to learn new ideas and new information regarding the open discussion.

Generally, I learned from my lapses, and I did improve those things. I should also be open-minded about the negative comments and keep a position on everything that I will do. I have to accept and apply the suggestions and feedback wholeheartedly so that I will be able to develop as a professional teacher. I was so glad and proud of myself to be able to finish almost three months of training and practice despite the challenges and struggles I encountered so far.

5.11 The Private School Environment

Jayrome Nuñez is a practice- teacher in a private secondary high school

Back in my days as a student-teacher (ST), I have been exposed to pedagogical scenarios because we did extension services to adopted communities of our college. My college is a private Catholic institution run by nuns and education students are required to join community programs to do sort-of-teaching to children in those communities. Before my formal practice teaching, what we did were mostly on literacy, catechism, and hygiene.

As my university offers education from Kinder to college, most of my teaching exposure was to private education in the Philippines. And this private education is one of the top and most expensive institutions in the north-western Philippines. I took a Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSE), major in English because I thought at that time that it was cool and easier to study since the English language is widely used globally so it could also open more opportunities when I graduate.

To be able to complete my degree, I needed to complete a full five-month formal practice teaching in the high school department of our university. During that time, I was only expecting to take one or two hours of teaching per day, which includes observations and assisting my cooperating teacher (CT) to give time for coaching and lesson preparation with my cooperating teacher. CT is the employed individual who will serve as the mentor in the actual teaching simulations. The relationship between CT and ST last from the beginning of the semester until the last day which will culminate in a final demonstration. The final demonstration is when the ST will take charge of a full hour (and a half) of class to the selected section wherein a group of observers which are composed of the high school principal, the college dean, and a program coordinator will seat and watch the ST deliver the final teaching requirement.

It may sound eerie but during my day, I was the only practice teacher from the program because I did it in the first half of the year while the rest did it in the second half (the normal schedule). I was an irregular student back then; I got fewer course units (credit hours) recommended per semester compared to my peers because I was a working student. I needed to earn a living while studying, so I needed to compromise my study loading, in return I had to stay a little longer in college.

I could remember it clearly that my practice teaching turn was kind of anticipated because one of the English teachers was set to take the leave due to her pregnancy. To cut it short, instead of hiring a paid substitute teacher, they utilized me to replace the teacher's classes but with less paperwork because I wasn't allowed to do it yet. I took more classes as recommended, there were not many coaching sessions because I was performing as a quasi-teacher. It was like I was put into war without proper training.

The teacher I substituted was handling grades 7 and 8 (junior high school), however not all classes were given to me, they were distributed among other

English teachers, especially the star sections. I remember clearly, that I had one class in the G7 and two classes in G8. English classes in the Philippines are combined with literature and English language structure. In G7, they are required to take Philippine Literature while in G8, they get to study Asian Literature.

In terms of physical setup, the school was fairly equipped with the latest technology that would aid the students and teachers in delivering classes. Classrooms are well ventilated; the number of students was in t30s0, and students are well behaved since it's a private and catholic school they were taught to display utmost respect to the teachers. So, in terms of dealing with untoward behaviors, I couldn't recall having a hard time during my stay.

In my situation, I didn't have to prepare the lessons myself because all lessons were already prepared, and I just needed to review them and deliver them. However, one of the things that I had struggled with was physical exhaustion. Teaching is rea exhausting job because in the Philippines does not just involve delivering the lesson but also dealing with other side jobs, like being a homeroom adviser, attending club meetings, and even staying beyond office hours just to make sure students were safe while school premises. And I had to deal with full teacher responsibility while still attending college and taking my shifts at work.

In terms of lesson delivery, as expected I got nervous at first especially when someone (a teacher) watches me teach all the time, it gradually changed when they knew that I could handle the classes alone already and they barely visited me in classes – I was like free. They trusted me enough that I could take on those tasks with minimal supervision. I did not get much of the coaching sessions too, because my CT needs to attend her classes plus additional classes from the other teacher who took a leave of absence in the English department. What I needed to do was just deliver the lesson of the day and prepare my formative assessment since the

summative assessment was prepared by the actual teachers with more experience and training.

During the last weeks of my quasi-teaching capacity, I had to remind my CT that my college semester was about to end because basically, I was still a college student without any formal educational qualification to teach. Now, here comes the final stage where I need to demonstrate my skill to a full audience of professionals and my students. I had to take some time off from my job to prepare for the lesson of my choice. I didn't know but I still got the chills, it's different when a teacher is alone with students and when being watched by other colleagues, let alone me, a college student?

The day arrived, students were at their best behavior, and the panel of judges was set at the back and ready to watch me, I was ready and at the same time nervous. I took the safest and the easiest lesson I could think of to deliver in a one-hour reading class. It was in grade 7. The lesson I chose was tag questions. I need to deliver it within an hour including the assessment after the class.

I could vividly remember what I did to springboard the lesson to be able to introduce the lesson. I presented them with physical tags of bags, shirts, and grocery items and asked them its name. It was fun to look at, but I was shaking to my core. Then, we discussed the topic of the day and did our reading activity which relates to the tag questions. I also asked them to pair for some activities and final practice tasked them to accomplish the activities in the tin textbook.

After the demonstration, I was called to the faculty room with all these r teachers, who gave congratulatory messages to me for successfully passing my practicum. In addition to that, my CT and the subject coordinator also personally thanked me for doing beyond my responsibility and taking real classes in the absence of their colleague. I didn't get any more suggestions, instead only wished for luck in my board examinations to get my license.

After finishing my final college requirement, I officially ended my college journey in October of 2010. And In April of 2011, I passed my professional qualification examinations for teachers in the Philippines.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Practice teaching enables interns to experience the actual classroom teaching and school paperwork preparation. Aside from the technical aspects of the internship process, it prepares the student-teachers as well in the different course of school activities that will immerse them in the process of management.

This study portrays the personal attestation of both authors from the school facilities up to the lesson delivery of the competencies. Participants highlighted those misconceptions that arise due to the changing orders and systems implemented by the different acting heads. Another is that interns are only tasked to execute the assistantship work of the cooperating teacher. However, in a real scenario, interns are given much more responsibility and management skills that allow them to be actual teachers delivering the lesson prepared beforehand. It possesses advantageous aspects as it forces the intern to embody becoming a real teacher in an uncontrolled situation. Teaching materials like books, modules, and assessment sheets differ from the different schools they were assigned to but both follow the same list of competencies to be implemented. School facilities vary based on the immediate and future needs of the learners. Lesson planning required by the public schools is way different from being used in the private schools since learning resources where lessons are based from has different content.

Generally, the personal experiences of the different interns vary from the school environment, protocols, and learning resources of the school assigned. The different practice-teaching experiences narrated by the interns that will have a common phenomenon will be a strong determinant of a certain situation. When the majority of the studies agree on the same

reason, appropriate actions and resolutions will be addressed.

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